

IP4OS

Innovation, Sovereignty, and Open Science

Roundtable convened by the Canadian Embassy

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1. Context and Aim

This policy brief documents the outcomes of a roundtable on Innovation, Sovereignty, and Open Science, convened by the Canadian Embassy on 4 March 2026. The session brought together 12 participants from academia, government, research institutions, and legal practice, with the aim of examining the limitations of traditional intellectual property frameworks and exploring open science as an alternative model for knowledge production and innovation. A cross-cutting concern was how middle powers such as Canada and Spain can retain strategic value from the knowledge they generate, rather than seeing intellectual property migrate abroad – particularly the United States of America.

2. Summary

The roundtable identified a growing misalignment between the patent system and contemporary research realities. Participants highlighted that patents are costly to enforce, rarely yield commercial outcomes for universities, and can actively discourage knowledge-sharing. Open science models – illustrated by AlphaFold and a UK pharmaceutical initiative operating without IP protections – were presented as viable alternatives. Key barriers discussed include cultural resistance among researchers and firms, regulatory fragmentation within the EU, geopolitical tensions, and underdeveloped commercialisation infrastructure. The session concluded with three priority recommendations: strengthening IP and open science education for researchers, expanding legal advisory capacity around open science governance, and repositioning open science as a strategic opportunity rather than a competitive risk.

3. Participants

The roundtable was convened on 4 March 2026 by the Canadian Embassy and brought together 12 participants from academia, government, research institutions, and legal practice. Institutions represented included:

- Canadian Embassy
- Spanish Ministry of Economy, Trade and Business
- Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT)
- Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)
- McGill University
- Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M)
- University of Kiel (CAU)
- Zentrum für konstruktive Erziehungswissenschaften (ZKE)
- Miller International Knowledge (MIK)
- Pérez Llorca
- Centre for Open Science (COS)

The session opened with remarks by Richard Gold (McGill University), who introduced the themes of innovation, technology sovereignty, and open science, followed by contributions from each participant sharing perspectives from their respective sectors.

4. Context and Canadian Position

The session was inaugurated by the Canadian Ambassador, who outlined Canada's strategic positioning in global research and innovation.

Canada is actively aligning with Horizon Europe Pillar 2, particularly in areas related to interoperability and federally funded research and development.

Two key dynamics were highlighted:

First, Canada has established the world's first dedicated Ministry of Artificial Intelligence (AI), which plays a direct role in funding and shaping national AI initiatives.

Second, both Canada and Spain face a similar structural challenge: although they produce significant scientific knowledge and research output, a substantial portion of their intellectual property ultimately migrates abroad - particularly to the United States. In other words, more patents leave these countries than remain within them.

This reflects a broader phenomenon in global innovation systems where knowledge production and patent ownership do not always coincide. For example, the Netherlands owns more US patents than it invents, demonstrating how intellectual property ownership can shift geographically through investment, acquisitions, and commercialization processes.

5. Illustrative Open Science Models

Two successful open science initiatives were cited as examples of alternative innovation models.

The first is a UK-funded pharmaceutical research initiative in which nominated drugs are developed without allocating intellectual property rights. All outputs are made open source. Despite the absence of traditional patent protections, the program has been described as highly successful.

The second example is AlphaFold (2024), the AI system for protein structure prediction that is developed and maintained by Google DeepMind. The project relied on openly shared data and contributions from scientists worldwide and is now considered one of the most significant scientific breakthroughs of recent decades as evidenced by its developers winning the Nobel Prize in Chemistry in 2024.

These cases demonstrate that scientific progress and economic value can emerge from collaborative and open research environments, challenging assumptions that innovation must be driven by exclusive intellectual property ownership.

6. The Case for Open Science

A central theme across the roundtable discussion was that the traditional intellectual property system - particularly patents - often fails to reflect the realities of contemporary research and innovation.

Several limitations of the patent system were highlighted.

First, patents are extremely costly to enforce. Defending or prosecuting a patent infringement case in the US can cost approximately \$3 million per side, making legal protection effectively inaccessible to small and medium-sized enterprises, independent researchers, and projects focused on niche diseases or public health priorities. Without a credible threat of enforcement, patents represent a cost to not only the developer but research labs without any benefit.

Second, most university patents never lead to commercial outcomes. Many institutions accumulate patent portfolios that remain unused while consuming administrative resources.

Third, the current system often produces inefficient duplication of research. Because negative results and unsuccessful experiments are rarely shared, private laboratories frequently repeat work already performed elsewhere. Open science could significantly reduce this waste by making data and experimental outcomes more accessible.

In some cases, participants noted that patents are intentionally written in ways that obscure the underlying knowledge, including deliberate typographical errors or misleading descriptions designed to hinder replication. Such practices undermine the broader objective of scientific progress.

One participant highlighted an emerging trend in the private sector: corporate mergers and acquisitions are increasingly driven by access to talent and expertise rather than patent portfolios. Firms with deep knowledge and skilled teams - even without significant patent holdings - are attracting major investment.

As Gold summarized:

“What we need is a diversity of approaches. No one knows exactly how open science will work, but what we need is openness to openness.”

7. Barriers and Challenges Identified

Despite its potential benefits, several barriers to implementing open science were identified during the discussion.

7.1. Cultural and Behavioural Barriers

Many researchers lack clear guidance on when patenting is appropriate or necessary, and they often develop strong emotional attachments to their discoveries. This can create resistance to alternative models of knowledge sharing.

Similarly, firms frequently fear that making code, methodologies, or datasets public will eliminate their competitive advantage. Several speakers argued that this perception is often exaggerated, particularly (but not exclusively) when open science is limited to pre-competitive stages of research.

Additionally, the language of patents continues to dominate investor discussions, even in cases where patents offer limited practical protection or strategic value.

7.2. Structural and Geopolitical Barriers

Structural challenges were also discussed.

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) was identified as an example of a major initiative that has struggled with both technical interoperability issues and political coordination challenges.

Participants also noted that growing geopolitical tensions are making governments and funders more cautious about adopting open knowledge frameworks, particularly in sensitive technological areas.

Another major challenge is regulatory fragmentation within the European Union. Currently, more than one hundred regulatory instruments affect science and technology policy. There are increasing calls to simplify this framework rather than expand it further, including through initiatives such as the proposed Digital Omnibus.

Funding dynamics also play a role. Institutions such as MILA in Montreal or the Vector Institute in Toronto have found it easier to raise capital by relocating to the United States, highlighting the structural advantages of the American investment ecosystem.

7.3. Financing and Commercialisation

Open science can facilitate relationship-building and collaborative research, which can in turn unlock new funding opportunities. However, participants emphasized that the

infrastructure required to commercialize open research outputs remains underdeveloped.

One participant argued that the central issue facing Europe is insufficient investment rather than excessive regulation. Maintaining technological competitiveness will require ensuring that both companies and talent remain within European innovation ecosystems.

8. Key Perspectives from Participants

Several participants offered distinct perspectives on how open science could be implemented more effectively.

One participant emphasized that legal professionals must be involved early in the development of open science frameworks. Lawyers should not merely react to new models but actively participate in designing them.

Another participant highlighted that researchers and small businesses often fail to use existing open science platforms effectively, partly because these platforms are perceived as opaque or “black boxes.” This person also stressed that security considerations must coexist with openness, particularly in a context of geopolitical tension.

One participant, representing the non-profit sector, argued that the central challenge is cultural transformation: making open science the default rather than the exception. This person cited META’s experiment with open science practices within Instagram as an example of ongoing experimentation in the private sector. The participant also emphasized that high-quality, trustworthy data is essential, noting that AlphaFold succeeded largely because it relied on reliable underlying datasets. Finally, this person called for the creation of a metascience alliance to facilitate cross-sector learning.

A participant, representing academia, emphasized that EOSC evolved from a technical initiative into a political and cultural project. Institutions had to shift from a mindset of exclusive ownership toward a culture of shared knowledge. This person also highlighted the concept of knowledge valorisation, noting that researchers rarely consider how knowledge should strategically circulate or be deployed. As a potential compromise between openness and protection, the person proposed shorter copyright protection periods, such as five years, which is currently not possible under current international agreements, most notably Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIP).

From the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)’s perspective it was noted that many SMEs misunderstand patents as a form of protection. In reality, smaller firms rarely have the resources to enforce patent rights against larger competitors. This person argued that the key challenge is convincing researchers of the tangible benefits of open science and answering a fundamental question:

“If I do not patent, what do I gain?”

Finally, a participant representing the public sector in the areas of economics, trade, and business emphasized the importance of including economics, trade and business, governance actors in these discussions. This perspective highlighted that such institutions hold direct competences in business development, economic security, and strategic autonomy. It was stressed that, more than ever, international relations requires an integrated approach combining economic, trade, technological, and innovation intelligence.

From this viewpoint, trade policy can serve as a key instrument to address several of the structural challenges discussed, including the relatively small size of companies in countries such as Spain and Canada, their position as net importers or exporters of strategic technologies, disparities in access to capital, the need to accelerate AI adoption among SMEs, and the opportunity to strengthen bilateral cooperation between Canada and Spain (and the EU).

Moreover, the participation of economic and trade actors enables the integration of scientific perspectives on open science into broader economic and trade policy frameworks, particularly in relation to technological sovereignty and strategic autonomy.

9. Session Conclusions

Participants identified three priority areas for future action.

Education

Researchers - particularly early-career scientists - should receive better training on intellectual property options, open science tools, and pathways for commercialising research outputs.

Legal Innovation

Law firms should play an important role by developing new advisory services focused on building open science governance structures, rather than solely defending traditional IP frameworks.

Business Advisory Capacity

Innovation advisors should be equipped to present open science not as a threat to competitiveness, but as a strategic opportunity for collaboration, talent attraction, and technological leadership.

10. Concluding Reflection

The discussion concluded with a broader strategic observation: unless middle powers adapt their innovation systems - through collaboration, open science, and stronger ecosystems - they risk continuing to generate knowledge that ultimately strengthens competing economies.